

Optimizing ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators for wavelength-shifting-fiber neutron detectors

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Abstract-- In this paper we compare the performance of grooved and flat ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators in a wavelength-shifting-fiber (WLSF) detector. Flat ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators with the thickness $L=0.2-0.8$ mm were characterized using photon counting and pulse-height analysis and compared to a grooved scintillator of approximately 0.8 mm thick. While a grooved scintillator considerably increases the apparent thickness of the scintillator to neutrons for a given coating thickness, we find that the flat scintillators perform better than the grooved scintillators in terms of both light yield and neutron detection efficiency. The flat 0.8-mm-thick scintillator has the highest light output, and it is 52% higher compared with a grooved scintillator of same thickness. The lower light output of the grooved scintillator as compared to the flat scintillator is consistent with the greater scintillator-WLSF separation and the much larger average emission angle of the grooved scintillator. We also find that the average light cone width, or photon travel-length as measured using time-of-flight powder diffraction of diamond and vanadium, decreases with increasing L in the range of $L=0.6-0.8$ mm. This result contrasts with the traditional Swank diffusion model for micro-composite scintillators, and could be explained by a decrease in photon diffusion-coefficient or an increase in micro-particle content in the flat scintillator matrix for the thicker scintillators.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is important for neutron scattering community to develop alternative neutron detection technologies due to shortage of ³He gas [1]. Scintillator-based neutron detectors are promising and enabling technologies [2]. At the Spallation Neutron Source (SNS), Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), a wavelength-shifting-fiber (WLSF) neutron detector with 0.3 m² per module was developed [3] and has been deployed for time-of-flight (TOF) neutron powder diffraction (POWGEN, VULCAN). However,

Manuscript received November 15, 2015. This manuscript has been authored by UT-Battelle, LLC under contract DE-AC05-00OR22725 with the U.S. Department of Energy.

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these detectors have relatively low efficiencies at short neutron wavelengths ($\lambda \leq 1.8$ Å), which is an important wavelength band for the POWGEN instrument. It is a serious challenge to design an efficient WLSF detector at shorter wavelengths with reduced ghosting (mis-assigned neutron events) [4] and without a loss in spatial resolution. This issue can be mitigated through the optimization of ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators. Though the particle ratio of ZnS and ⁶LiF in the scintillator was initially optimized in terms of neutron detection efficiency [5], less was done in optimizing the thickness of scintillators. To increase the neutron absorption efficiency at shorter neutron wavelengths (below 1.8 Å), V-grooved ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators were used at POWGEN and VULCAN beamlines at SNS. Unfortunately, the V-grooved scintillators have low light output.

In this work, we report thickness-dependent light output, neutron absorption efficiency, and photon travel length [4] of flat and grooved ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators obtained using a moderated ²⁵²Cf neutron source and two SNS beamlines (VULCAN and POWGEN). We used a potential-well model and a photon-diffusion model under weak disorder to explain the results. We found that thicker ($L \geq 0.6$ mm) flat scintillators can better satisfy our needs in increasing neutron detection efficiency while reducing the fraction of ghosting images without degradation in spatial resolution.

II. EXPERIMENTS

The neutron absorption and scintillation light output of ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators were measured using a moderated ²⁵²Cf source, and also at the CG1A ($\lambda=4.26$ Å) and HB3 ($\lambda=1.0$ Å) beam lines at the High Flux Isotope Reactor (HFIR), ORNL. Flat high-density ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators with a size of 51 mm x 51 mm and thicknesses $L=0.2-0.8$ mm were purchased from Eljen Technology (Sweetwater, Texas, US). Two grooved ZnS/⁶LiF scintillators with a 51 mm x 2 mm size were cut from a large scintillator screen purchased from AST Ltd. (now Scintacor, UK). An end view of the grooved scintillator is shown in Fig. 1. The average effective

thickness normal to the screen surface is 0.81 mm, while the average thickness of scintillator screen at the 45° direction relative to the normal is 0.57 mm.

Fig. 1 End view of an AST grooved scintillator. The average thickness values along different directions have a unit of millimeter. The substrate is an aluminum plate.

Neutron transmission was measured using a 1 cm x 1 cm aperture in the front of an 8-atm ^3He tube in a transmission configuration. A scintillator/PMT assembly was installed in front of the ^{252}Cf source to measure both light output and neutron count rates. In the light output measurement, the signal from the PMT (ET Enterprises 9124B) was directly fed into a constant-fraction discriminator (CFD, Ortec 584, voltage threshold=10 mV) and an analog counter. After subtracting the background, the net photon count rate was obtained. In the neutron count rate measurement, the pulse-height spectra were collected in a detection chain consisting of a fast amplifier (Ortec 460), a shaping amplifier (Ortec 572A, 10- μs shaping time), and a multi-channel analyzer. Pulse-height spectra under irradiation of a ^{60}Co source were also collected to determine a threshold channel N_{th} to separate neutron events from gamma-ray background for each scintillator. The neutron count-rate was calculated by integrating the pulse-height spectrum starting from the threshold channel $N_{\text{th}}=300$ as shown in Fig. 3(a). The relative values of light output and

neutron detection efficiency (or neutron count rate) of each scintillator were calculated using the flat Eljen 0.5 mm-thick scintillator as a reference. The above measurements were repeated 2-3 times; and average values of neutron absorption efficiency, relative light output, and relative neutron count rate were obtained.

The light response function (LRF) is defined as the distribution of the end-to-end distances from the locations of neutron absorption to photon detection projected along the x -axis [4]. The photon travel-length is the average full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) of the LRFs at different x -pixels [4]. We measured the LRFs from the neutron events compromising the diffraction patterns of diamond and vanadium powder samples. Four detector modules containing flat Eljen scintillators with $L=0.2$ -0.8 mm were installed to collect the diffraction patterns of diamond and vanadium at VULCAN and POWGEN beamlines. Among the four modules, one has a scintillator screen composed of three panels of $L=0.2$, 0.3, 0.4 mm (Tri-Scintillator 1), and the other $L=0.6$, 0.7, 0.8 mm (Tri-Scintillator 2), respectively. The types of fiber mapping, scintillator, scintillator-fiber configuration, and PMT are listed in Table I. Two types of PMTs were used, a Hamamatsu H8711 MA-PMT for the v3.1 module and Electronic Tube (ET) 9124B discrete PMTs for v3.0 modules. The MA-PMT has 16 pixels with two vertically adjacent anodes connected so that each of the 8 combined-pixels accommodates 21-28 ends of WLSFs. Four MA-PMTs were used in the v3.1 module. The v3.1 and v3.0 has the same fiber mapping [4].

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF V3 DETECTOR MODULES

Module	Encoding	Scintillator Thickness (mm)	Front ^(a)	Back ^(b)	Fiber-scintillator gap (mm)	PMT	PMT-voltages
1	v3.0	single, 0.2-0.4	X		4.3	9124B	1010-1470 V
2	v3.1	single, 0.5	X		4.3	H8711-300	850-1000 V
3	v3.0	double, 0.5	X	X	4.3	9124B	1190-1520 V
4	v3.0	single, 0.6-0.8	X		3.5	9124B	980-1430 V

^(a)Front, ^(b)back: the scintillator is in the front or back side of the cross-fiber array.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The neutron absorption efficiency vs. scintillator thickness L is shown in Fig. 2. As expected the neutron absorption efficiency increases with L . Based on the neutron absorption efficiencies for $L=0.2$ -0.5 mm at $\lambda=4.26$ Å and 1.0 Å (data not shown here) and the neutron absorption cross-section of ^6Li , we calculated the ^6Li concentration in the $L=0.2$ -0.5 mm samples and used the average value ($1.63 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) of ^6Li concentration to evaluate the neutron absorption efficiency at $\lambda=1.8$ Å for $L=0.2$ -0.8 mm.

As shown by the solid line in Fig. 2, the measured neutron absorption efficiencies with the ^{252}Cf source are in a good agreement with the expected values for $L=0.2$ -0.5 mm and 0.8 mm. It indicates that the average neutron wavelength from the moderated ^{252}Cf source is about 1.8 Å. In Fig. 2, the neutron absorption efficiency of the AST grooved sample is close to that of the flat Eljen 0.8-mm-thick ones, suggesting that the ^6Li concentration in the grooved AST scintillator is close to those in the flat Eljen ones.

Fig. 2 Neutron absorption efficiency for Eljen HD scintillators and an AST grooved scintillator. The solid line is the expected ^{252}Cf -neutron absorption efficiency based on the average ^6Li concentration measured for $L=0.2-0.5$ mm at $\lambda=1.0$ Å and 4.26 Å.

The relative light output and neutron detection efficiency vs. L are shown in Fig. 3(a). Though the relative light output has a large variation at $L \leq 0.7$ mm, the Eljen 0.8-mm-thick sample has the largest light output. This observation is supported by the highest neutron detection efficiency from the flat Eljen 0.8-mm-thick sample as shown by the pulse-height spectra in Fig. 3(b). The correlation between the relative light output and neutron detection efficiency is shown in Fig. 3(c). The general trend is that the light output increases with the neutron detection efficiency, as observed previously in the study of uniformity of neutron efficiency of WLSF detectors [4]. In addition, the grooved AST scintillator has a light output which is only about 66% that of flat Eljen 0.8-mm-thick scintillator, though it has an effective thickness close to $L=0.8$ mm. The grooved scintillator has a larger average air-gap away from WLSFs (or PMTs) than the flat scintillator, so it has a lower light output compared with the flat scintillator with the same particle concentrations and thickness based on a potential-well model of a leaky waveguide [6-7]. This model also explains the increased light output by applying a transparent optical-coupling film between the scintillator and the PMT window as observed in our scintillator test. In addition, the larger collection angle θ (relative to the normal direction of the scintillator plane) from the grooved scintillator may also result in lower light collected by the WLSFs. Based on Lambert's cosine law [9], the collected light intensity is proportional to $\cos\theta$. The grooved scintillator has smaller $\langle \cos\theta \rangle$, so the WLSFs will

collect less photons compared with the flat scintillator with $L=0.8$ mm.

Fig. 3 (a) Relative photon count rate and relative neutron count rate vs scintillator thickness L . The reference is the Eljen HD 0.5-mm-thick sample. A ^{252}Cf source was used for the measurements. (b) Pulse-height spectra of flat Eljen scintillators with $L=0.5-0.8$ mm and the AST grooved scintillator; the insert shows the linear scale of pulse-height spectra. (c) Relative photon rate (or light output) vs. relative neutron rate (or efficiency).

Fig. 4 Normalized photon yield Y_N vs. L , where Y_N is the relative photon count rate (under ^{252}Cf irradiation) divided by the measured neutron absorption efficiency in Fig. 2. The solid curve is from a simple photon-diffusion model. The empty square and circle represent Y_N of the AST grooved scintillator at thicknesses at 45° to and normal to the screen surface, respectively; and the dashed line represents the range of equivalent thicknesses of the grooved scintillator.

The relative light output normalized by the neutron absorption efficiency, Y_N , was calculated vs. L , as shown in Fig. 4. The normalized photon yield Y_N reflects the photon generation capability under the irradiation of the same amount of absorbed neutrons. Obviously Y_N decreases with scintillator thickness. The $Y_N(L)$ curve can be fitted with a simple photon-diffusion model [9] for a flat slab, i.e., $Y_N(L) = C/(L+2z_0)$, where C is a constant, and z_0 is a parameter related to the mean-free-path (MFP) l of scintillation photons by the relation $z_0 = 0.71l$. The MFP is defined as the mean distance between two subsequent elastic scatterings of photons in microcomposite scintillators. The flat scintillator can be modeled as a semi-infinite flat slab in which the total transmission intensity only depends on the scintillator thickness. The fitted $z_0 = 126 \pm 38 \mu\text{m}$ for $L = 0.2-0.7$ mm, which gives the MFP $l = 177 \pm 54 \mu\text{m}$. Therefore, the mean-free-path l is much larger than the average wavelength ($\sim 0.43 \mu\text{m}$) of emitted photons, which indicates a weak-disorder limit for the light scattering in the ZnS^6LiF scintillator [9,10]. The Y_N of Eljen 0.8-mm-thick scintillator is a little higher than the expected value from the diffusion model, in contrast with the AST grooved scintillator. Compared with flat scintillators, the lower photon yield of grooved scintillator indicates that it has lower neutron detection efficiency [4] when applied on a WLSF detector under the same conditions.

To check whether thicker scintillators lead to degradation of spatial resolution, we measured the

light response functions (LRFs or light cones) and obtained the average photon-travel length $\langle L_p \rangle$ [4] for $L = 0.2-0.8$ mm using the neutron events in TOF powder diffraction data of vanadium and diamond. As shown in Fig. 5, the average photon-travel length $\langle L_p \rangle$ has a slight increase with L when $L \leq 0.5$ mm. Classical diffusion models for microcomposite scintillators including Swank model [11] or Mie-scattering theory [12] can explain the increase of $\langle L_p \rangle$ with L only at $L \leq 0.5$ mm, but not the decrease in $\langle L_p \rangle$ with L at $L = 0.5-0.8$ mm. The decrease in $\langle L_p \rangle$ at larger L may be understood by photon diffusion under weak Anderson localization and photon absorption [10]. The photon diffusion coefficient D may have the following scaling relation $D \sim L^{-\alpha}$ ($\alpha > 0$) [10,13] due to a ballistic-to-diffusive transition (or from 2D to 3D) of the photon transport occurred at $L/l \approx 3$ as predicted by a radiative transfer theory and/or first-principle calculations of microscopic scattering theory (ladder approximation for the Bethe-Salpeter equation) [13]. Under the condition of weak disorder, the diffusion equation is still applicable for the scintillators with $L/l \geq 3$ [13], i.e., $L \geq 0.53$ mm. Compared with the scintillators with $L < 0.5$ mm, the thicker scintillators ($L > 0.5$ mm) have a lower diffusion coefficient, which leads to narrower photon diffusion profiles (LRFs) from these scintillators. More evidence is needed to verify this explanation. Nevertheless, narrower LRFs from scintillators with $L \geq 0.6$ mm are expected to increase the spatial resolution because of enhanced accuracy of neutron positioning [14].

Fig. 5 Average photon travel length $\langle L_p \rangle$ vs. scintillator thickness L obtained from Gaussian fits of LRFs. Lorentzian fits of LRFs give a similar trend of $\langle L_p \rangle$ vs. L .

It is also interesting to study the scintillator-thickness dependence of ghosting when the neutron position is determined by traditional maximum-

photon algorithm (MPA) and centroid algorithm (CEA)[4]. The MPA for the 0.5-mm-thick scintillator

Fig. 6 TOF diffraction patterns $I(x,t)$ at $x=22, 77, 121$ pixels (at group boundaries) for flat scintillators with $L=0.6-0.8$ mm. $I(x,t)$ was obtained from neutron positions calculated by maximum-photon algorithm (MPA) and centroid algorithm (CEA). The ghost imaging (indicated by arrows) appears at $L=0.6$ mm, but greatly reduced at $L=0.7$ and 0.8 mm.

based module produces an observable fraction of ghosting for diamond powder at VULCAN beamline (BL7), while the CEA can greatly reduce the ghosting fraction [4]. There is a clear trend of ghosting fraction produced by MPA vs. scintillator thickness L . Fig. 6 shows the diamond powder diffraction pattern $I(x,t)$ at three group boundaries (GB) obtained from module 4. At $L=0.6$ mm, ghosting from MPA still exists though its fraction is reduced compared with $L=0.5$ mm [4]. However, at $L=0.7$ and 0.8 mm, the fraction of ghosting from the MPA is greatly reduced as compared with $L \leq 0.6$ mm. This is expected from the LRF vs L as shown in Fig. 5, i.e., a wider LRF will result in greater uncertainty in determining the G-PMT value when a neutron hits a group boundary [4]. Another factor responsible for the ghosting is the lower average photons collected per neutron event from the 0.6 mm-thick scintillator. Using the same photon thresholds in the neutron positioning (MPA), the average total-number of photons per thermal neutron is 78, 86, and 87 for scintillators with $L=0.6, 0.7,$ and 0.8 mm, respectively. The lower the total-number of photons, the less accurate the neutron positions and the higher is the probability of ghosting. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 6, the centroid algorithm (CEA) can avoid the occurrence of ghosting at GB for $L=0.6-0.8$ mm at about 10% loss of the neutron detection efficiency. Therefore, the optimized scintillator thickness for VULCAN is $L \geq 0.7$ mm.

We also tested module 4 (TriScinti 2) at POWGEN beam lines using PMT voltages about 7% higher than the values listed in the Table I. Compared with the 0.7-mm and 0.8-mm thick scintillators, the 0.6-mm thick scintillator has higher neutron detection efficiency for three neutron bandwidths with the central-wavelengths of 0.50, 2.67, and 4.78 Å. At the POWGEN beam line, ghosting is much less severe than at VULCAN, probably due to the lower neutron flux from the sample at POWGEN. Therefore, we choose the optimum thickness ($L=0.6$ mm) of the scintillator for POWGEN.

IV. CONCLUSION

We studied the light yield, neutron absorption, and neutron detection efficiency of $ZnS^{6}LiF$ scintillators with thicknesses $L=0.2-0.8$ mm that are used for WLSF neutron detectors. We found a good linear relation between the neutron detection efficiency and light output. More interestingly, we found the flat 0.8 mm-thick Eljen HD scintillator has much higher light yield compared with an AST grooved scintillator of an equivalent thickness. Based on the neutron detection efficiency, light output, and image quality

(spatial resolution and ghosting), we conclude that a flat scintillator with the thickness of 0.6 mm or higher can increase the detection efficiency of epithermal neutrons, reduce the ghosting fraction from the MPA, and maintain the spatial resolution.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge much experimental help and discussion with K. An, S. Chi, K. C. Donahue, A. Huq, C. Montcalm, H. D. Skorpenske, A. D. Stoica, and T. Visscher, and comments on the manuscript made by K. W. Herwig. Research conducted at Oak Ridge National Laboratory's Spallation Neutron Source and High Flux Isotope Reactor was sponsored by the Scientific User Facilities Division, Office of Basic Energy Sciences, United States Department of Energy.

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